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Information Sources and Postpartum Depression Knowledge in Northern Nigeria: A Structural Equation Modelling Approach

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Abstract

In most low-resource contexts, postpartum depression is poorly identified, and maternal mental health literacy is constituted by the multidimensional social and communication networks. This study explores the effect of information sources and risk communication on predicting knowledge of postpartum depression among Northern Nigerian women. The survey was cross-sectional among women of reproductive age in Niger and Yobe States, and the data were analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling to determine how well the various communication pathways predicted each other. Based on the Health Belief Model, the structural model indicates that interpersonal networks, medical personnel, religious leaders, radio, and digital platforms have significant and positive predictive influences on postpartum depression knowledge that jointly explain a large percentage of the variance in the awareness of women. The strongest predictive value is communication by medical staff and online platforms, which is followed by family networks and religious leaders, which shows the key role of trust and accessibility in health beliefs formation. On the contrary, the predictive influence of newspapers, magazines, television, indigenous media and opinion leaders in the model is weak and statistically insignificant. This study has shown that perceptions of susceptibility, severity and benefits of postpartum depression are socially mediated and not acquired individually through an explicit modelling of the explanatory power of the various sources of communication. The results give evidence-based recommendations on effective maternal mental health interventions that focus on trusted interpersonal, religious and medical communication avenues to enhance awareness and prompt action to postpartum depression.

Keywords: Postpartum Depression, Help-Seeking Behaviour, Information Sources, Maternal Mental Health, The Extended-Health Belief Model (E-HBM).

Background

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a psychological condition associated with pregnancy, childbirth, and the manner in which a woman is treated after delivery. It is a recognised global public health concern affecting women across societies, with empirical studies indicating a global average prevalence rate of approximately 17.7% (Hahn-Holbrook, 2018). The burden of PPD is, however, more pronounced in Africa, particularly in Northern Nigeria, where the total fertility rate (TFR) is estimated at 7.6 children per woman. This high fertility pattern exposes women to repeated childbirth within short intervals, thereby increasing their vulnerability to PPD (NDHIS, 2025).

Although it is severe, PPD in Northern Nigeria has been misinterpreted as a spiritual attack or a test of maternal endurance, which results in stigmatisation of affected women (Adeyemi, 2022; Omale et al, 2025). These misconceptions are greatly influenced by the lack of educational opportunities, high reliance on the remedies of religion and culture, low levels of income to access medical care, and a lack of healthcare services. Therefore, most women do not perceive PPD as a health issue and do not apply relevant professional care (Omale et al, 2025).

Whilst there has been a wealth of psychological, midwifery, and medical literature and practice on PPD, the paper theorises PPD through a communication lens, namely, maternal mental health communication. This solution is based on the fact that the treatment of health conditions including PPD involves beyond medical or psychotherapeutic treatment on its own. Communication is an essential part of health management since it defines awareness, understanding, and making health-related decisions (Burgner, 2020; Finset et al., 2020).

The fact that PPD is still seen as a spiritual experience or a normal thing about motherhood by Northern Nigerian women is of serious concern. The inability to communicate the symptoms, warning signs, and sources of help in a clear and culturally appropriate manner increases the chances of untreated PPD developing into more serious illnesses, including postpartum psychosis. This underscores the relevance of risk communication in conveying the health hazards associated with untreated PPD. Providing timely, accurate, and context-sensitive information, risk communication can support informed help-seeking decisions, encourage positive behavioural change, and at the end reshape women's perceptions and understanding of PPD.

Research Gaps

The gap in the research is the minimal academic focus on the study of postpartum depression through the communication lens, especially how risk communication can influence awareness, perception, and help-seeking behaviour of women in Northern Nigeria. Current literature centres mostly on medical and psychological aspects, and there is still a gap in the knowledge of how misconceptions, stigma and late treatment of PPD may be overcome through culturally based maternal mental health communication.

Research Question

The following research questions drive this investigation:

1. What are the information sources women rely on regarding postpartum depression in Niger and Yobe States, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between information sources and the level of knowledge of postpartum depression among women in Yobe and Niger State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Indigenous Media as Sources of Information About Postpartum Depression

Indigenous media can serve both as an avenue through which information on postpartum depression (PPD) can be disseminated in Northern Nigeria and as an instrument in dealing with stigma and raising awareness. For example, community elders and griots can use oral traditions and storytelling to narrate about maternal mental health using local proverbs and folktales as a way to start a conversation about PPD. Just as community radio stations can broadcast programs about PPD with healthcare professionals and survivors, to help educate the listeners about the symptoms of this condition and possible treatments (Busolo & Manalo, 2023).

Furthermore, information can be disseminated through personal stories and articles about PPD published in local Hausa newspapers and magazines like *The Daily Trust* Hausa Edition for literate audiences to read local papers and magazines. In addition, performances and cultural representations, such as masquerade festivals and dramas, can be translated to depict PPD challenges through artistic expressions already familiar to the audience, to inform people that help for PPD is available (Hefler et al., 2019; Busolo & Manalo, 2023).

Through indigenous social media platforms, such as WhatsApp groups and Facebook pages, women can establish forums of experience sharing and resource access to build peer support networks (Hefler et al., 2019). Traditionally, symbols and art such as Adinkra symbols or beadwork can also be incorporated into health campaigns to visually transfer messages about maternal mental health; they are more relatable and accessible (Ejere & Adeleke-Sola, 2023).

Theoretical Framework

The Health Belief Model (HBM) was developed in the early 1950s by social psychologists Godfrey Hochbaum, Irwin Rosenstock, and Stephen Kegels to explain why individuals adopt or resist health-related behaviours. The model, originally used to explain reactions to public health programmes, postulates that four fundamental perceptions, susceptibility to a condition, severity of its consequences, perceived benefits of acting and perceived barriers to acting are used to explain behaviour, later with cues to action and self-efficacy.

In its simplest form, the HBM presupposes that individuals do not react to health risks in an automatic fashion; instead, they give risk its meaning with references to social and informational contexts thus created. This renders the model especially useful to this study, which adopts approaches to postpartum depression (PPD) as a phenomenon mediated by communication but not an entirely clinical phenomenon. The elements of the family networks, religious spaces, media, peers, and health care experiences are the sources of information that form the perceptions of vulnerability, seriousness, and help-seeking of females.

When interpreted in terms of communication, information sources act as the medium through which the constructs of HBM are put into action, undermined or transformed. Normalisation of emotional distress messages minimises perceived severity, whereas culturally plausible communication may enhance perceived benefits and self-efficacy. The HBM, therefore, offers a

practical base of the influence of communication processes on the organisation of maternal beliefs and the help-seeking behaviour in relation to postpartum depression.

The present study expands the Health Belief Model by anticipating communication as the process by which the health beliefs are built, bargained, and practised. Instead of considering the perception of susceptibility, severity, and benefits as a cognitive process, the model frames them as a socially mediated process that is influenced by information sources found within the family, religious, media, and healthcare communication settings. In this respect, postpartum depression is tackled not as a health condition but as a communicative process wherein the meaning, risk, and response are negotiated in a continuous manner.

Materials and Methods

The research used a quantitative survey design to investigate maternal mental health communication and postpartum depression (PPD) among Northern Nigerian women of childbearing age. The study was carried out in Niger and Yobe States, respectively, while the sample of participants was purposely selected. The study area included urban and rural Local Government Areas, in Bosso and Bida (Niger State), and Damaturu and Machina (Yobe State) to represent a variety of communication contexts.

The study population consisted of women who were aged 15 to 49. The Taro Yamane was to determine the sample size of 399 respondents at the 95% level of confidence and a margin of margin of error (5 percent) and multiplied by 30 percent to give 519 participants to the survey. The sample was not excessively large and therefore representative of study locations.

The information was gathered with the help of a structured questionnaire, which was used to measure socio-demographic factors, the sources of information about PPD, as well as the knowledge about postpartum depression. The tool was translated into Hausa and confirmed by health communication and maternal health specialists. The survey was administered face-to-face by trained field assistants.

The analysis of the data was done with the help of the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The PLS-SEM was considered appropriate given the exploratory nature of the model, the focus on prediction, and the non-normal distribution of the data. Standard indicators formed the measurement reliability and validity, whereas hypothesised relationships were tested by bootstrapping procedures. The Covenant University Research and Ethics Committee approved the study, and informed consent was obtained by all the participants.

Presentation of Data

The demographic profile from the two selected states is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Yobe State	Niger State	Total
	Age		
18-25	5.4%	9.4%	14.8%
26-33	10.0%	32.6%	42.6%
34-41	9.4%	20.4%	29.9%

42-49	3.9%	8.9%	12.7%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%
Educational Qualifications			
No formal education	2.3%	3.3%	5.6%
Primary School Leaving Certificate	1.9%	3.7%	5.6%
SSCE	5.6%	38.9%	44.5%
Ordinary National Diploma	5.4%	12.1%	17.5%
Higher National Diploma	7.7%	6.7%	14.5%
B.Sc, B.Ed, B.Tech	3.7%	6.2%	9.8%
M.A., M.Sc., M.Ed., M.Phil., PhD.	2.1%	0.4%	2.5%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%
Employment Status			
Entrepreneur	2.3%	6.4%	8.7%
Artisan	2.7%	35.5%	38.2%
White collar job	4.8%	5.0%	9.8%
Student	5.6%	4.6%	10.2%
Unemployed	7.1%	5.8%	12.9%
Self-employed	6.2%	14.1%	20.2%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%
Monthly Income			
Less than 50,000 Naira	6.0%	48.0%	53.9%
50,001 to 100,000	8.1%	10.6%	18.7%
100,001 to 200,000	5.0%	2.3%	7.3%
200,001 to 300,000	6.6%	10.2%	16.8%
300,001 and above	3.1%	0.2%	3.3%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%
Marital Status			
Single	7.3%	0.6%	7.9%
Married	18.3%	69.9%	88.2%
Divorced	1.5%	0.4%	1.9%
Widowed	1.5%	0.4%	1.9%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%
Religion			
Christianity	6.9%	2.9%	9.8%
Islam	19.8%	68.4%	88.2%
Traditional	1.9%	0.0%	1.9%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%
Number of Children			
None	6.9%	2.9%	9.8%
1-2	19.8%	68.4%	88.2%
3-4	1.9%	0.0%	1.9%
5 and above	11.9%	30.1%	42.0%
Total	28.7%	71.3%	100.0%

The demographic characteristics depict that the population is mostly young, married, and high fertility, with a low level of education and income (53.9%), who earn less than ₦50,000. Such a scenario strengthens dependence on interpersonal, religious communication networks, making family and faith-based sources the major decoders of maternal health experiences, including postpartum depression.

Inferences on the socio-demographic of respondents in both the Niger and Yobe States as indicated in Table 1 portrays that Niger State forms the majority of the sample (71.3%), indicating that there is a more available or engaged population, whilst the high proportion of married respondents (88.2) between the two states indicates the existence of deep-rooted social norms of early marriages, but the large proportion in the 18-33-year bracket (57.4) indicates that the population is in the prime age group of reproduction.

To say the least, the statistics are truly striking with a young overwhelmingly married population with the majority of them in prime years of bearing children being the least educated and the poorest, thus suggesting that in Northern Nigeria, family structures function more as mechanisms of survival than as pathways for socioeconomic mobility. Only 2.5% received a postgraduate degree and are able to earn #300,001 and above (3.3%). It can be deduced that the data might be low level of education being the factor that has caused the high percentage of artisans who have incomes below #50,000.

More than that, the extraordinarily low divorce rate in relation to the exceedingly high rates of marriage and the fact that polygyny is accepted in the Islamic religion, which is the highest in terms of religion (88.2%), suggests that the separation of marriages is not accepted culturally or religiously, which has created a social back-lash where marriage is maintained structurally rather than emotionally. This is also contrasted by the skew in the age group of younger women (26-33); they occupy the huge percentage of the sample, not necessarily due to influence of data collection but due to desirability of younger brides in society. This can be a practical way of marginalising the older wives which is not really divorcing them; this creates an invisible group of invisibly married and conjugally marginalised women that are not even counted by the cumulative statistics of marital status data. Through this, even the appearance of stability in marriage conceals a relationship in which serial polygyny, facilitated by older women is a factual alternative of divorce and directly affects the age structure, and strengthens the relationship between the youth of females, marriage structure, and high fertility.

Table 2: Respondents’ Sources of Information on Postpartum Depression Experience

S/N		Strongly	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Television has provided me with information on postpartum depression.	14.0	19.8	11.2	54.2	0.8	3.1220	.83665

2	Radio programs have provided me with information on postpartum depression.	14.8	36.2	14.8	32.5	1.7	3.3988	.82952
3	The newspaper has provided me with information on postpartum depression.	3.1	6.2	13.5	72.3	5.0	2.4701	.99738
4	I trust information about postpartum depression shared on social media.	13.7	26.4	6.6	51.5	1.9	3.4836	.91492
5	I trust the information about postpartum depression shared on Websites.	46.6	41.4	4.2	6.0	1.7	3.2524	.91737
6	I rely on medical personnel for information on postpartum depression.	13.5	40.2	3.3	32.6	2.7	3.4682	.93332
7	Government officials have provided me with information on postpartum depression.	11.8	76.3	5.4	71.3	1.3	4.1973	1.08592
8	Non-governmental organisations have provided me with information on postpartum depression.	4.6	86.1	3.3	4.6	1.3	3.8805	.60976
9	Family and friends(s) provide me with accurate information on postpartum depression.	51.4	19.7	22.0	3.3	3.7	3.9744	.94027
10	Traditional	7.1	80.7	5.4	4.2	2.3		

	healers/community elders are an important source of information about postpartum depression.						3.8651	.69826
11	Relative(s) have provided me with information on postpartum depression.	3.9	72.8	5.4	16.0	1.9	3.6069	.86749

12	My spouse has provided me with information on postpartum depression.	3.7	87.9	3.5	3.3	1.7		
							3.8844	.58795
13	Neighbours(s) have provided me with information on postpartum depression.	1.9	15.0	7.5	67.9	7.9		
							2.3545	.89698

Test of Hypotheses

Ho: There is no significant relationship between information sources and the level of knowledge of postpartum depression among women in Yobe and Niger State, Nigeria.

The first hypothesis examined the resultant effect and relationship between information sources and the level of knowledge of postpartum depression among women in Niger and Yobe States. A standardised questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect data from women in Niger and Yobe States. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS- SEM) was used to examine the relationship between these variables. Figure 1 depicts the relationship between information sources and the level of knowledge of postpartum depression among women in Niger and Yobe States. Importantly, all the measures related to the information sources and the level of knowledge of postpartum depression showed factor loadings higher than the minimum threshold of 0.70.

Also, the SmartPLS-SEM software used for the analysis produced the construct validity and reliability. As stated in the literature, the figure must be more than 0.5 to determine AVE. While the Cronbach alpha value must be 0.7 and above, the standard for composite reliability must be above 0.8.

Table 3: Construct Validity and Reliability for Hypothesis One

Constructs	Loading	VIF	P value	AVE	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
	≥ 0.7	<3.0	<.05	≥0.5	≥ 0.8	> 0.7
Family & Friends (FF)				0.741	0.896	0.832
FF1	0.883	1.555	0.000			
FF2	0.850	1.761	0.000			
FF3	0.849	1.523	0.000			
Indigenous Media (IM)				0.675	0.861	0.759
IM1	0.838	2.001	0.000			
IM2	0.821	1.335	0.000			
IM3	0.805	1.762	0.000			

Magazines (MZ)				0.738	0.894	0.824
MZ1	0.816	2.010	0.000			
MZ2	0.908	1.544	0.000			
MZ3	0.851	2.104	0.000			
Medical Personnel (MP)				0.690	0.870	0.775
MP1	0.815	1.680	0.000			
MP2	0.809	1.671	0.000			
MP3	0.867	1.915	0.000			
Newspaper (NP)				0.735	0.893	0.819
NP1	0.862	1.874	0.000			
NP2	0.836	1.577	0.000			
NP3	0.873	1.605	0.000			
Opinion Leaders (OL)				0.768	0.908	0.848
OL1	0.821	1.578	0.000			
OL2	0.910	1.913	0.000			
OL3	0.895	2.046	0.000			
Radio (RD)				0.801	0.924	0.876
RD1	0.906	1.982	0.000			
RD2	0.895	1.300	0.000			
RD3	0.884	1.704	0.000			
Religious Leaders (RL)				0.711	0.881	0.797
RL1	0.882	1.912	0.000			
RL2	0.849	1.569	0.000			
RL3	0.797	2.044	0.000			
Social Media (SM)				0.777	0.912	0.855
SM1	0.898	1.474	0.000			
SM2	0.924	1.776	0.000			
SM3	0.819	1.558	0.000			
Television (TV)				0.735	0.892	0.817
TV1	0.747	1.812	0.000			
TV2	0.923	2.210	0.000			
TV3	0.891	1.785	0.000			
Websites (WS)				0.854	0.946	0.914
WS1	0.952	2.311	0.000			
WS2	0.876	2.123	0.000			
WS3	0.942	1.565	0.000			
Postpartum Depression Knowledge (PDK)				0.854	0.946	0.914
PDK1	0.785	1.676	0.000			
PDK2	0.711	2.344	0.000			
PDK3	0.800	1.785	0.000			
PDK4	0.776	1.811	0.000			
PDK5	0.842	2.003	0.000			

PDK6	0.836	1.975	0.000
PDK7	0.728	2.123	0.000
PDK8	0.817	2.145	0.000
PDK9	0.841	2.069	0.000
PDK10	0.870	2.452	0.000
PDK11	0.857	2.111	0.000

Table 3 depicts the factor loadings for each measurement item regarding information sources and the level of knowledge of postpartum depression among women in Niger and Yobe States. The study assessed the validity and reliability of the instrument using Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Cronbach's Alpha (CA), applying threshold values of 0.80, 0.50, and 0.70, respectively. In addition, convergent validity was examined to determine the construct validity of the instrument.

Convergent validity indicates the extent of the specificity of the relationship between the constructs of the source of information and knowledge of postpartum depression in women in Niger and Yobe States. The loadings of the factors were between 0.747 and 0.952, which shows a high degree of reliability. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was employed to assess the presence of common method bias (CMB). While a VIF value of 1 indicates a complete absence of collinearity, many studies recommend a threshold of 5.0 for acceptable levels. According to Jeng (2023), the safest and most conservative range lies between 2.5 and 5. The VIF values for all components across the evaluated variables are well below the conservative benchmark of 5.0. This indicates that collinearity is minimal and confirms that the study is not significantly influenced by common method bias. However, the interplay between information sources and postpartum depression knowledge among women in Yobe and Niger State is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Path Co-efficient and P-values for Information Sources and Postpartum Depression Knowledge

FF: Family & Friends, IM: Indigenous Media, MZ: Magazine, MP: Medical Personnel, NP: Newspaper, OL, Opinion Leaders, RD: Radio, RL: Religious Leaders, SM: social media, TV: Television, WS: Websites, PDK: Postpartum depression knowledge

Evaluation of the Inner Structural Model and Fitness

The significance of the inner structural model was evaluated using path coefficients. In Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), bootstrapping plays a crucial role in determining the statistical significance of the model's relationships. The default bootstrapping technique was used in this research, with 5,000 subsamples. The inner structural model shows the correlation between the sources of information and knowledge of postpartum depression. The model fit indices of the measurement model were all within acceptable ranges and better than the existing cutoff cutoffs as demonstrated in Table 4.

Table 4: Model Fit

Model Fit Index	Measures	Benchmark	Model Value
	SRMR	< 0.08	0.078
Absolute Fit Index	Chi-Square	<3.0	2.224
	GFI	≥ 0.90	0.929
Incremental Fit Index	CFI	≥ 0.90	0.944
	NFI	≥ 0.90	0.950
Parsimony Fit Index	PCFI	≥ 0.50	0.647
	d_ ULS	≥ 0.50	0.711
	d_ G	≥ 0.50	0.581

SRMR: Standardized Root Mean Squared Residual, d_ ULS: the squared Euclidean distance, d_ G: the geodesic distance, NFI: Normed Fit Index, CFI: Comparative Fit Index; PCFI: Parsimony Comparative Fit Index, GFI: Goodness of Fit Index.

This paper utilised three main types of model fit measures absolute fit measures, incremental fit measures, and parsimony fit measures according to the suggestions by Hair et al. (2022). Shi and Maydeu-Oliveres (2019) explains that absolute fit indices are used to determine the extent to which the sample data fits qualitatively theoretical forecasts of models. The value of SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) of the information sources and the knowledge about postpartum depression had 0.078 that is lower than the 0.08 threshold, which is an indication of an acceptable fit. The Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI) was 0.929, which is larger than the 0.90 benchmark, which goes more to affirm model adequacy. Moreover, there is also the CMIN/DF value indicates a good model fit.

Incremental fit indices are used to estimate how much better the proposed model is compared to a base case model where the variables are supposed to be uncorrelated. In both the Normed Fit Index (NFI) and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), with a value of 0.90, generally indicates an acceptable fit (Sathyanarayana & Mohanasundaram, 2024). The value of NFI of 0.950 in the study indicates that the model is highly appropriate to the data.

Parsimony fit indices allow comparing models and their effectiveness in describing the population. The Parsimony Comparative Fit Index (PCFI) is 0.647, which is higher than the recommended minimum of 0.50. Fornell and Larcker (1981) explain the RMSR (Root Mean) as follows: The SQRT value (0.078) is within the acceptable range and CMIN/DF. The value of CMIN/DF (0.078) is at the acceptable range. The value of 2.228 is less than the upper value of 3.0 which indicates a good model fit.

In addition, it is generally used to determine model acceptance with NFI, GFI, and CFI values high 0.90. Other indicators like d ULS and d G are also used to assess discrepancies in model estimates (Hair et al., 2022). All these findings show that the model meets the necessary statistical parameters and fits the data well.

Predictive Relevance and Effect Size

Q² values are employed in Partial Least Squares Structural Equation (Cheah et al., 2020). Modelling (PLS-SEM) in order to evaluate the predictive relevance of constructs and the data points of their indicators. A Q² value exceeding 0 represents predictive relevance. In this study, the Q² value for the predictive validity of such construct was high, as postpartum depression knowledge was 0.659. within the PLS path model. The f² (f-square) statistic was also used to calculate effect sizes. Fornell and Larcker (1981) gave the following classification of f² values: The significance level of 0.02 is a small effect, the significance of 0.15 is a medium effect, and the significance of 0.35 is a huge impact. The f² values in this study are as follows: 0.542 (FF), 0.519 (IM), 0.322 (MZ), 0.643 (MP), 0.342 (NP), 0.441 (OL), 0.472 (RD), 0.344 (RL), 0.672 (SM), 0.762 (TV), and 0.507 (WS). These values reflect significant effect sizes, which suggests that model shows great practical importance (Cohen,1988).

Table 5: Path Coefficient for Information Sources and Postpartum Depression Knowledge

Variables	Path Co-efficient	R-Squared	Std. Dev	T-Statistics	P-value	Remark
FF – PDK	0.617	0.381	0.014	6.055	0.000	Sig.
IM – PDK	0.085	0.007	0.025	1.951	0.110	Not Sig.
MZ – PDK	0.017	0.003	0.022	1.748	0.452	Not Sig.
MP – PDK	0.688	0.473	0.024	6.054	0.000	Sig.
NP – PDK	0.033	0.002	0.025	1.750	0.188	Not Sig.
OL – PDK	0.099	0.010	0.031	2.001	0.078	Not Sig.
RD – PDK	0.331	0.110	0.026	8.686	0.000	Sig.
RL – PDK	0.310	0.096	0.025	7.453	0.000	Sig.
SM – PDK	0.217	0.048	0.017	5.711	0.000	Sig.
TV – PDK	0.088	0.008	0.033	1.954	0.251	Not Sig.
WS – PDK	0.227	0.051	0.022	3.667	0.000	Sig.

FF: Family & Friends, IM: Indigenous Media, MZ: Magazine, MP: Medical Personnel, NP: Newspaper, OL: Opinion Leaders, RD: Radio, RL: Religious Leaders, SM: Social Media, TV: Television, WS: Websites

The outcome of the path coefficients among the various sources of information and postpartum depression (PDA) is shown in Table 5. The results show that several sources of information made a significant contribution to postpartum depression and others did not show statistically significant effects. To begin with, Family and Friends (FF) were very strong and significant modification on postpartum depression awareness, where the path coefficient is 0.617, and the R-squared is the value of 0.381, and a p-value of 0.000. This implies that close social interpersonal communication networks are important in enhancing knowledge of mothers about postpartum depression.

Similarly, strong and statistically significant influence on postpartum by Medical Personnel (MP) was also significant depression awareness ($\beta = 0.688$, $R^2 = 0.473$, $p = 0.000$). This implies that Medical professionals are very effective as expert health educators who promote communication enhancing awareness. Further significant results were observed for *Radio (RD)* ($\beta = 0.331$, $R^2 = 0.110$, $p = 0.000$), *Religious Leaders (RL)* ($\beta = 0.310$, $R^2 = 0.096$, $p = 0.000$), *Social Media (SM)* ($\beta = 0.217$, $R^2 = 0.048$, $p = 0.000$), and *Websites (WS)* ($\beta = 0.227$, $R^2 = 0.051$, $p = 0.000$). These results

indicate the relevance of mass media (particularly radio), digital, and reliable community sources (religious leaders) in informing women about postpartum depression. On the other hand, some of the sources did not exhibit a statistically significant impact.

These include *Indigenous Media (IM)* ($\beta = 0.085$, $p = 0.110$), *Magazines (MZ)* ($\beta = 0.017$, $p = 0.452$), *Newspapers (NP)* ($\beta = 0.033$, $p = 0.188$), *Opinion Leaders (OL)* ($\beta = 0.099$, $p = 0.078$), and *Television (TV)* ($\beta = 0.088$, $p = 0.251$). The non-significant findings would suggest that these channels can contribute to the spreading overall information but are less useful to exert a significant impact on knowledge of postpartum depression in this matter.

Discussion of Findings

The sources of information on postpartum depression (PPD) among women in Northern Nigeria were examined in this study, and the influence of these sources on knowledge. The results indicate a communication ecosystem in which efficacy is controlled by cultural legitimacy and not informational accuracy alone. The quantitative findings give a definite ranking of impact. Family, friends, and traditional elders became the most approved sources (Mean scores: Family/Friends 3.97, Spouse 3.88, Traditional Healers 3.87), which is a result that directly matches the demographics profile of a majorly married (88.2%), lowly educated population in which power is concentrated in kinship and experience. Such dependence on informal networks is well-documented in other such contexts; as Fisher et al. (2012) observed, such sources are supportive but tend to be perpetuating distortions through framing PPD as a spiritual situation.

The power of these is statistically validated by the path results of the PLS-SEM model relational channels. Result show that there was a strong and significant influence of Family and Friends (FF) on PPD knowledge ($\beta = 0.617$, $p = 0.000$). Formal mass media such as newspapers, on the other hand, will have the same effect (NP, 0.033), directly reflected was the lack of significance in $p = 0.188$) and television (TV, $\beta = 0.088$, $p = 0.251$). In terms of the education level, the sample with 44.5% of them had SSCE as their highest level of education. This is a vivid example of what Abdulbaqi et al. (2023) posit as one of the most drastic gaps in formal information dissemination, especially in the countryside.

The main paradox is that the message of government and NGOs is highly recalled (Mean: 4.20 and 3.88) vs. their inability to significantly predict in the model. This indicates a systemic losing touch between dissemination of messages and meaningful integration, and it implies that awareness campaigns do not translate into actionable knowledge when they do not take the form of trusted interpretive communities. In other words, knowledge do not result to action without normative approval.

The results are empirical evidence of the digital divide model hypothesised by Sawyer et al. (2010). Women living in the city with higher education levels tended to use digital sources of information especially social media ($\beta = 0.217$, $p < 0.001$) and websites ($\beta = 0.227$, $p < 0.001$) to play an active role in interpreting and making sense of their experiences after childbirth. to actively interpret and make meaning of their postpartum experiences. The statistically significant positive coefficients suggest that the greater the access to, and recognition of, digital platforms, the greater the ability of women to contextualise and recognise symptoms of postpartum depression. On the other hand women in the rural environment on the other hand depended more on traditional and community-based information. Radio exposure was strongly positively related to postpartum depression knowledge (β

= 0.331, $p < 0.001$). In a similar study carried out by Omale et al, (2025) provided a qualitative angle to this finding. According to the study the qualitative explanations indicated that the information provided was usually general and was not diagnostic specific. Therefore, this information was often filtered by cultural and spiritual contexts. In this scenario, religious leaders became significant knowledge brokers, who did not appear as secondary substitutes but as primary caretakers. Their leadership indicates high rates of trust, accessibility, and offering of holistic factors of support that most of the women felt was not well tackled in the formal clinics.

the rejection of the null-hypothesis (H_0) proves that there is an important relationship with the source of the information and postpartum depression knowledge. Interestingly, it is important to note that the trend of the substantial predictors family and friends (FF), medical professionals (MP), radio (RD), religious leaders (RL), social media (SM), and websites (WS) against the background of the non-significant ones like newspapers (NP), television (TV) and magazines (MZ) highlights an important observable idea that it is not the communication medium that matters in developing the effectiveness of information sources, but concerns of trust, availability and relevance to the context. Embedded sources are the most dominant in terms of impact on knowledge acquisition compared to those sources that are transduced by media that are considered to be remote or impersonal.

The insignificant impact of indigenous media does not make it less culturally relevant but underscores its restricted ability to transmit biomedical mental health knowledge in quantifiable forms. Although these avenues are very trusted, they tend to position postpartum distress symbolically as opposed to clinically, which supports the meaning but not necessarily medical recognition and help-seeking.

The results thus indicate a modification of the Health Belief Model (HBM) by placing risk communication as a construct of placement. The perception of susceptibility and severity are found to be socially mediated by culturally authoritative means, whereas perceived barriers go beyond individual issues to structural and socio-cultural barriers found in the FGDs. Successful prompts to action should therefore be incorporated into trusted channels of information, including messages that are mutually communicated by health workers and religious leaders, to evoke the help-seeking behaviour.

The research adds to the body of knowledge in communication by illustrating that in Northern Nigeria, knowledge about postpartum depression is influenced not only by the availability of messages but also by the communicative legitimacy.

The study contributes to a continued advancement of a Health Belief Model, placing maternal mental health into the context of culturally based communication systems, which is achieved by empirically mapping the roles played by trusted sources of information in the activation of health beliefs and help-seeking behaviours.

To sum up, this research is helpful in providing some empirical research evidence that combating PPD in this regard is not a matter of lack of information and more of a matter of communication congruency. The solution lies in the ability to intervene beyond general awareness efforts to strategically incorporate the biomedical knowledge into the available trusted systems of family, faith, and community leadership, thus closing the gap between the clinical evidence and the cultural reality on the ground.

Theoretical implications and theoretical contributions to knowledge based on findings from the Study

Fig. 2: The Study's Proposed Model. The Extended-Health Belief Model (E-HBM)

Source: *Omale et al (Author's work, 2025)*

(This is an original Model developed from the findings of the study, and has not been published elsewhere, hence no reference yet)

The advancement of the Health Belief Model shows that the views of women and how they respond to postpartum depression in the Niger and Yobe States are informed by contextual and risk-based factors. Displayed information of health professionals, NGOs, family networks, and religious groups mediates the interpretation of emotional and psychological changes following the birth of a child. It is these communication processes that form perceptions of susceptibility, perceived severity and beliefs regarding postpartum depression that ultimately define whether PPD is perceived as a medical condition or viewed as a spiritual or social problem. Less communication towards medicalising PPD means that women feel vulnerable and have low knowledge about the seriousness of the condition.

Perceived barriers are also pointed out by the model as a key bottleneck. Stigma, cultural demands, and financial constraints to lack of supportive healthcare systems are just some of these obstacles, which lead to deteriorating willingness or capacity of women to access professional care. Contrarily, action cues, like antenatal sessions, peer narratives, or NGO outreach can stimulate awareness and action, although such signals are usually intermittent and strongly reinforced.

These interacting factors, in a nutshell, influence help-seeking behaviour and define whether women can receive care or have to further cling to spiritual or traditional solutions. The success of this process will lie in the manner, in which communication will take care of cognitive beliefs as well as the contextual barriers.

That is, this longer model emphasizes that not just awareness but strategic communication that develops self- efficacy, reforms cultural discourses, and places postpartum depression in the context of the continuum of maternal health is needed.

Empirical Implications

The results present empirical data that the knowledge of postpartum depression in women in Northern Nigeria is rather influenced by particular sources of information than by the general exposure to the media. The statistically significant effects were found in interpersonal networks, medical personnel, religious leaders, radio, and digital platforms which indicates the importance of the significance of trustful and accessible communication channels in maternal mental health education. On the other hand, the non-significant effect of the newspapers, magazines, television, and the use of indigenous media implies that the receipt of the messages does not imply the acquisition of meaningful knowledge. The findings indicate the necessity of empirically supported communication practices, putting credibility, cultural legitimacy, and interpersonal mediation as a priority in low-resource environments (Fisher et al., 2012; Abdulbaqi et al., 2023).

Implications for the Application of the Health Belief Model

The results reaffirm the applicability of the Health Belief Model in the understanding of the knowledge of postpartum depression in culturally engrained communication frameworks. The views of vulnerability and severity among women are constructed largely through the interpersonal,

religious, and healthcare networks of trust as opposed to the official mass media. The distress prevailing in families and religious leaders tends to be normalised, thus reducing the perceived severity, and communication by medical staff and trusted online resources promotes the perceived usefulness and self-efficacy to seek help. Those findings prove that the HBM constructs are not individual mental processes but are the ones that are socially mediated by the information sources that are legitimate in a certain context. The successful implementation of the model in maternal mental health interventions, thus, can only be achieved by incorporating risk communication in trusted social and institutional systems to impact health beliefs and encourage informed care-seeking.

Interpretation of Hypothesis Test Results

The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the sources of information and the knowledge about postpartum depression was rejected in part. The outcome from the PLS-SEM findings shows that the variables that most strongly predicted the knowledge of postpartum depression among women in Niger and Yobe States were family and friends, medical personnel, radio, religious leaders, social media, and websites. However, indigenous media, newspapers, magazines, opinion leaders, and television did not show statistically significant effects. This trend indicates that trust, cultural closeness and interpersonal interactions are more predictive determinants of maternal mental health knowledge within the context of the study as opposed to formal or print-based sources of communication.

Implications for Policy and Practice

Policymaking-wise, the results reveal the shortcomings of general campaigns of awareness that mainly use the formal mass media. Maternal mental health interventions can rather be combined with healthcare providers, religious and community-based interpersonal networks as major avenues of delivering postpartum depression education. Healthcare workers and faith leaders during training programmes should be provided with culturally sensitive communication strategies that help to present postpartum depression as a valid and curable health problem. In practice, maternal mental health messaging, as an element of antenatal and postnatal care, religious events, and community meetings, can be used to increase knowledge acquisition and decrease stigma (Abdulmalik et al., 2016; Dixon and Dantas, 2017).

Integrating Theory and Communication Implications

The paper has shown that maternal mental health outcomes cannot be simply defined as products of individual cognition, and they are instead entrenched in communication systems that define the risk perception and response to risk. This study advances the application of the Health Belief Model by empirically demonstrating how communication channels mediate key belief constructs in a maternal mental health context by empirically relating the information sources to postpartum depression knowledge. This study contributes to the field of communication scholarship because it frames risk communication as a primary mechanism in the context of maternal mental health promotion in culturally diverse and complex environments.

Limitation of the Study

The study is limited despite the contributions it makes. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to do causal inference, and the use of self-reported data could be susceptible to recall or

social desirability bias. Although the purposive sampling method is appropriate in the context, it constrains the ability to make generalisations about the results outside of the context of Niger and Yobe States. Also, the research was concerned with the knowledge outcomes, but not with the actual help-seeking behaviour. Future studies can use longitudinal or mixed method designs to investigate how exposure to communication can help in behavioural change over time.

Conclusion

The current study offers strong empirical data that women in Northern Nigeria base their knowledge of postpartum depression on culturally legitimate and trusted sources of information as opposed to being exposed to the formal media only. By placing maternal mental health in the context of a networking system of communication, the results show that the key to effective intervention is to bring the material of biomedical knowledge into a consistent relationship with already established social, religious, and interpersonal networks. The concept of the extended Health Belief Model presented as part of this study highlights the role of risk communication in changing the perception, eliminating the stigma, and encouraging informed help-seeking. Finally, the development of maternal mental health outcomes in such situations requires not only informative, but also culturally resonant and socially contextualised communication strategies.

Declarations

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Consent to participate

Respondents in the study were duly informed, gave their consent, and were presented with a consent form before participating in the study.

Availability of data and material

The dataset supporting this article has been made publicly available in the Mendeley Data repository, which can be accessed via the following link:

<https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/5msd75gyd3/1>

doi: 10.17632/hgsvfckpgn.1

Authors' Contributions

All authors were involved at every stage of the work with several meetings for academic brainstorming sessions, writing, analysis and fieldwork.

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